
The Impact of the British Council on Enhancing the EFL Learners' Vocabulary- A Quasi-Experimental Study

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Article Received: 25/04/2024

Article Accepted: 30/05/2024

Published Online: 31/05/2024

DOI:10.47311/IJOES.2024.6.5.202

Abstract:

Vocabulary is an essential tool in the process of language learning. It helps them in many ways, such as understanding passages, expressing thoughts and ideas, sharing information, understanding others, and building relationships. Therefore, general knowledge of the target language can help children develop all four language skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Unfortunately, some students sometimes have difficulty finding the right words because they do not have sufficient language skills. This study uses the British Council website to conduct a quasi-experimental study on university students learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL). In the first stage of the experiment, participants were given a pretest based on words. They were then divided into two groups: a control group and an experimental group, with or without online language testing. Finally, the Posttest was administered to two groups of students, and the results clearly showed the effect of the online test on the students in the experimental group.

Keywords: Vocabulary building; Language Learning; EFL; British Council Website; Pre-test; Post-test; Control Group; Experimental Group...

Introduction

English is the most spoken language in the world, with more than 1.5 billion people speaking it as a first or second language. Since most academic publications, research articles, and textbooks are written in English, English is the language of science, technology, international business, and the Internet. A student's future career will be affected by their knowledge of English, the language of instruction at colleges and universities in many countries.

Basic English

Learning English is the first step to learning English as a foreign language (EFL). Words that can be used to express the idea of an object or sentence in a language are called words. Lack of context prevents English EFL students from

communicating effectively because they cannot understand or express their emotions. The speaker cannot express his intention without words (Kitajima, 2001). Language deficiencies hinder students' ability to understand and communicate. Since words indicate what the speaker or writer wants to say, using the wrong words can affect communication (Ko & Goranson, 2014).

Vocabulary Learning Framework

Various principles apply to all methods for successful teaching. According to Wallace 1988, the principles are:

Purpose - what to teach, which words, how many to teach

Needs - language should meet the real needs and interests of the learners

Frequent exposure and repetition

Learning Vocabulary Online
Extensive research has shown that teaching new words in specific contexts through various activities provides the necessary strategies for better understanding and success. Considering technology's benefits to language learners and teachers, many tools and applications exist for teaching and learning languages.

Other forms of Internet advertising have been examined in experimental studies. Alakrashet et al. (2020) examined students using the Telegram application to increase communication. Test results showed that the app was an effective way to improve students' language scores and encourage them to learn languages in a more fun way. Ambarawati and Mandasari (2020) found similar results when they used the Cambridge online dictionary to help students learn words and sentences. Teachers and students can learn English in the classroom through various websites, applications, and online games on mobile devices. These services include Hello English, Duolingo, Kahoot, British Council, and many more. Derakhsan and Khatir (2019) believe that to promote learning and maintain students' interest, teachers should create activities that allow students to think about what is happening worldwide. For them, content is the basis of communication, a window into reality, emotions, and predictors of academic success. For example, Andreani and Ying (2019) found that interactive games such as PowPow encouraged students in grades 7 to 12 to learn English. Students can choose from various activities, including questions on English language practice (listening, speaking, reading, writing), sentences, vocabulary, and audio and photo-related topics.

The British Council website has questions on various topics that can be adapted to suit the curriculum or user preferences. After studying or taking the exam, students can view their results or scores on the British Council website. Anyone with an internet connection can download free exams at any time. The use and promotion of British English should begin as soon as possible so that students understand that English is more than American English.

British Council

It is a British organization that focuses on international culture and Education. It is an international social organization that was founded in 1934 and opened its first overseas office in 1938. It aims to deepen understanding of the UK and the English language and promote cooperation with the UK in science, technology, culture, and Education. It aims to change people's lives by giving them opportunities for culture,

community, Education, skills, and qualifications.

The British Council helps young people and students gain quality education and internationally recognized qualifications. It promotes cultural relations between people in the UK and other countries and broadens their knowledge of the English language. It also works with individuals to help them gain skills, language, confidence, and relationships. The British Council operates in more than 100 countries and works with people in more than 200 countries.

Features of the British Council

The salient features of the British Council are as follows. It
Evaluates the preparedness of the learners for high-stakes certification exams.
Determines advantages and disadvantages to help the learners teach.
Assesses educational initiatives.
Gauges pupils' development over a long course of study.

Background of the Study

It is not easy to learn English as a foreign language. Previous studies like Ajisoko (2020) and Amalia (2019) have found that several problems cause students to struggle when learning English. The first is a limited vocabulary, which makes it difficult for kids to comprehend the meaning of each word. The teacher's selection of uninteresting media is the second problem. Most institutions use the traditional method, which calls for students to write down their vocabulary and commit it to memory. When teachers employ traditional teaching methods, students need help understanding and remembering English vocabulary. The researchers deduced that the appropriate media or technique needed to be used based on the collected field data.

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis: There is no vast difference in their performance between the control group and the experimental group in the vocabulary pretest
Hypothesis-1: There is a difference in their performance between the control group and the experimental group in the vocabulary posttest
The British Council website greatly assists the vocabulary improvement among the experimental group of students.

Research Questions

Does the British Council Website help EFL undergraduate students improve their vocabulary?

Literature Review

Teaching English can be difficult, especially for students learning English as a foreign language. Traditional teaching methods seem ineffective because students cannot retain words. Adilbayeva et al. (2022) found that ICT is crucial for improving students' English language skills, especially reading skills. It is not only about improving students' reading skills but also focuses on improving students' motivation and desire to learn English. Finding reliable information providers has become easier with the help of the Internet. The Internet is open to everyone, and information can be processed.

There are many valuable websites about English courses on the Internet. The

British Council website is one of the online courses. Bashori et al. (2021) state that students' skills and motivation increase when they switch from traditional to web-based courses. According to the research, students experience significant improvements in language comprehension, enjoyment, and reduced stress.

In a study conducted on high school students, Sholiah and Wijaya (2020) found a significant difference in their pretest and post-test Posttest after using the British Council website for language learning. Alimi and Syafel (2013) came to the same point when they examined how primary school children learned from the BCC website. These studies show that online resources, such as the British Council website, can improve language skills at all levels of Education. Alakrashet et al. (2020) examined students using the Telegram application to increase communication. Test results showed that the app was an effective way to improve students' language scores and encourage them to learn languages in a more fun way. According to Toendan (2017), experimental research is "a study in which the effect of one variable on another variable is a controlled process."

Participants

The participants of this study were 42 undergraduate students learning English at the same level in the Faculty of Science and Humanities of Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University (PSAU). They were divided into two different groups: a control group and the experimental group. First, a pretest and a posttest were administered to two groups of students. While students in the experimental group were directed to the British Council's online communication program, students in the control group needed to be directed.

Pretest

This quasi-experiment aimed to find out if there was a difference between students using traditional laptops and other students using computers by linking to the British Council website. For this purpose, an experimental group and a control group were created. Both groups were administered the same pretest consisting of four parts of the language practice. In a typical classroom, students complete a pretest and Posttest, including instructions, in 20 minutes. Students in the experimental group took the same pretest and Posttest and completed the tasks in the same amount of time. The only difference is that the group offers Google links for the same topic. Students click on the link and complete the test with the help of the audio and video test.

Analysis of Pretest

Age of the students

18-20	21-23	Above 24
21 students	20 students	1

Table-1

Kruskal-Wallis Test Calculator

The present research has conducted the Kruskal-Wallis Test, a nonparametric alternative to the one-factor ANOVA test for independent measures. It evaluates the differences between three or more independent samples. H is the test statistic for the Kruskal-Wallis test, and the result is as follows.

	N	P-Value	H	Standard Deviation	Mean	Variance
Control Group	21	< .05	3.192	2.3	8	5.3
Experimental Group	21			2.3	8.3	5.4

Table-2

Therefore, the result reveals that the null hypothesis is proved correct. There was a difference in the performance between the control and experimental groups of students in the vocabulary-based pretest.

British Council

The British Council website has many benefits for language learners. There are many videos, audio, and texts for different levels, as well as online downloads and worksheets. It helps improve vocabulary, grammar, listening, reading, and writing anytime and anywhere. Free website. Online resources include many stories, songs, games, videos, downloadable worksheets, and online activities. Even children between the ages of five and twelve can register as members and share their thoughts and writings by leaving comments. A special section for parents and professionals also offers tips and advice on supporting their child's learning English at home.

British Council Activities

The website of the British Council carries out various initiatives to enhance English language learning among students globally.

It assists 100 million students worldwide online and connects over 4 million teachers and educators online annually – the world's largest teacher network.

It also offers over 4 million tests to professionals, university students, and secondary school students in over 140 countries, enabling them to accept internationally recognized UK qualifications. Work with English teachers, educators, and educational leaders.

British Council International Examination Services

The British Council offers the following services worldwide:

It develops and delivers innovative, flexible solutions that enable companies to check their customers to help them reach their maximum potential.

It recognizes 2,000 partner schools supported by the international community.

These services include security checks, online services, referrals, etc. takes place.

Fund managers are committed to working together to determine the best solution.

International Online

Tests are administered in more than 100 countries, with over 25,000 staff providing local language support at all times. Expertise and support from the field

Has more than 25,000 experienced customers, including supervisors and supervisors worldwide. Worldwide test distribution

Administers tests at locations in more than 100 countries and provides multilingual online proctoring services at various times.

.Local teams and customized solutions

On-site testing helps employees understand the local business and environment and create solutions that meet those needs. Be specific about organizations, high risks, appointments, testing when necessary, and meetings. Awarding bodies and foreign schools provide approximately 4.5 million tests, including vocational, university, English, and school tests.

Online proctoring

The British Council offers a range of online proctoring programs at various times around the world, allowing candidates to choose flexibly. Any test, anytime, anywhere. Work with the industry's most advanced technology partners to deliver secure, flexible, and scalable solutions.

Trust and Security

With 85 years of experience sending tests, it has solutions to ensure safety and usage. Get an online proctor solution. Flexibility and multi-modal delivery It features "just-in-time" online surveillance with automation, recording, and auditing and is flexible enough to deliver the program as soon as it is available on world test sites. Online service centers are located around the world and offer multilingual online proctoring services to 25,000 test takers.

Facilities available to candidates

Advanced online proctoring services mean candidates can continue their qualifications with more options and flexibility, allowing them to qualify with minimal disruption. Experienced experts monitor the accuracy of the security checkpoint. Technology as a Service

Service Assessment

It is front and center of change in Education and assessment, whether it is the upgrade of artificial intelligence, the move to digital authentication, or new technologies that support the integrity and security of student assessment. The technology and innovation team shares knowledge and understanding of new developments to help provide competitors with the best possible experience.

Exam Experience

The success of the previous exam day. Examples of AI applications currently being tested in delivery include facial recognition software and data analytics. Plan and maintain security and integrity.

AI in assessment

It has seen the use of AI in content creation for some time, but recent advances offer real opportunities for test owners to increase scale and reduce costs

while maintaining quality. Its Assessment Research Group provides insight into its latest studies of its use.

Posttest

Based on the vocabulary tests on the British Council Website, a posttest is conducted among both groups of students under the present study.

Data Analysis:

The present study presents the data analysis of the Posttest. It compares the scores obtained by the control and experimental group students in the Pretest and Test.

Analysis of Posttest

Table 3 presents the results obtained in the vocabulary posttest by both groups of students in the present study.

Comparison of Achievement Scores - Experimental & Control Groups

Tests	Groups	N	Std	Mean	Variance
Pretest	Control	21	3.4	10.1	11.7
	Experimental	21	2.3	8.3	5.3
Posttest	Control	21	2.5	9.6	6.9
	Experimental	21	1.1	18.8	1.2

Table-3

Note:*Max Score-20marks

Therefore, the marks scored by both the control and experimental groups of students reveal significant differences between them.

The performance of the experimental group of students who were exposed to the British Council Website links improved.

Findings

The study presents the pretest and post-test scores obtained by both the control and experimental groups of students in Table 8 and Table.

The findings show that there is no statistically significant difference in pretest scores between the control and experimental group students who worked on vocabulary.

Statistical Data Analysis

Each correct answer in the pretest was counted as one point, while the wrong answer was zero. The maximum score on the test was 20. Table 10 analyzes the comparative achievement of both groups statistically.

Thus, the posttest scores clearly show that the experimental group outperformed the control group, indicating that the British Council Website contributed to students' vocabulary learning. Further research is needed to fully investigate the efficacy of online vocabulary tests in vocabulary learning with a larger sample. The use of technology can be extended to other language skills as well.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the British Council website significantly affected students' English vocabulary. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that the British Council website considerably impacted students' vocabularies. The research question was answered, and the British Council website successfully improved and assisted students at the College of Sciences and Humanities for Girls in Wadi Addawasir,

KSA, in memorizing vocabulary, particularly descriptive adjectives.

It was also discovered that using the British Council website in class can be an effective teaching approach. This can occur when students simply complete student Worksheets during the treatment procedure. Their achievement scores increased after each meeting. The researchers discovered that the British Council website was effective as a new medium for learning English vocabulary.

This was evidenced by significantly higher posttest results, showing that this website was very helpful in learning English, particularly vocabulary; the primary limitation of this study is that it concentrated only on one class. This study's findings cannot be generalized (one group pretest-posttest). The lack of a comparison group increases the possibility of bias in the study. As a result, this study was only meaningful for one class of people. Thus, the researchers suggest that comparable research be conducted with more participants and different groups, such as control and treatment groups, in future studies to establish more justifiable generalizations and decrease data bias.

Vocabulary learning constitutes a fundamental and essential part of foreign language learning. Without vocabulary building, it is challenging to study grammar, speaking, listening, writing, etc. However, it is challenging to memorize a large amount of vocabulary. Learning new words, keeping them in mind, and recalling them when needed is relatively complex. With the help of innovative methods and materials that multimedia provides, language learning environments can be more colorful, motivating, and, at the same time, more supportive of students in the learning process. It isn't easy to learn a new language with so many words just by looking up a word or a term in dictionaries. Therefore, introducing words using a new method is necessary.

The online test is a tool that helps students focus on words because it is interactive and addresses almost all senses. While they try to understand the meaning of words associated with the scenes they watch on the screen, they are simultaneously exposed to the pronunciation of words and their written form. Vocabulary is thought to be an interesting and exciting activity for the students in the language learning process. Learning words in a context but with British Council website activities is thought to make learning more accessible for students.

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